

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Schoenoplectus corymbosus (Roth ex Roem. and Schult.) J. Raynal, a new weed in ricefields in India

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Large numbers of *Schoenoplectus corymbosus* (80.8/m²) in standing water of ricefields around Mudigere, Karnataka, India, affect crop growth and productivity.

The stout rhizomatous perennial grows to 70-110 cm ht (see figure). Stems are tubular and bear inflorescences about 15 cm from the tip. The inflorescence has 4-8 rays bearing clustered, often proliferous spikelets. Bracts are about 3 cm long, erect and rigid. Spikelets are ellipsoid, about 8 × 4 mm. Glumes are oblong, acute, with a narrow, minutely excurrent midrib. It has no bristles. The nut is obovoid, about 2 mm long, unequally triquetrous, black and shiny. Average dry weight of a single clump

Schoenoplectus corymbosus, a new weed in ricefields in the hill region of Karnataka, India.

is 9.72 g and there are around 39.2 stems in each clump.

In a rice plot with large numbers of *S. corymbosus*, yield was 30.7% less

than in a *S. corymbosus*-free plot.

This weed of rice is new for the hill region of Karnataka. □

Integrated weed management in transplanted rice

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The effect of manual (hand weeding), chemical (preemergence or postemergence herbicides), and cultural (azolla dual cropping) methods of weed control alone or in combination was studied in transplanted IR50 during 1985 kharif. The treatments were in a randomized block design replicated 3 times.

Weed flora at the experimental site

Effect of weed control treatments on transplanted rice. Madurai, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	12.94	6.4	687.4
Thiobencarb 1.50 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	14.20	6.3	659.4
Oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	15.06	6.2	641.5
2,4-D sodium salt 1.0 kg ai/ha + HW 40 DT	15.80	6.2	658.4
Azolla 1 t/ha 10 DT	34.20	5.1	508.0
Azolla 1 t/ha + HW 25 DT	17.20	5.6	565.5
Azolla 1 t/ha + HW 40 DT	16.60	5.7	586.8
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.66	5.8	606.2
Thiobencarb 1.5 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.34	5.8	594.2
Oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.86	5.7	581.6
HW 25 and 40 DT	13.20	6.3	664.2
Unweeded check	45.20	5.0	496.0
CD 5%	2.32	0.3	—

^a DT = days after transplanting, HW = hand weeding.

(clay loam) comprised *Echinochloa colona*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Sphaeranthus indicus*, and *Eelipta prostrata*.

Preemergence herbicides (butachlor, thiobencarb, and oxadiazon) were applied 3 d after transplanting (DT); postemergence herbicide 2,4-D was

applied 25 DT. Azolla was inoculated 10 DT.

Preemergence butachlor (1.25 kg ai/ha), thiobencarb (1.5 kg ai/ha), or oxadiazon (0.75 kg ai/ha) followed by 1 hand weeding (HW) 25 DT; or postemergence 2,4-D sodium salt (1.0 kg ai/ha) with HW at 40 DT controlled weeds as effectively as 2 HW (25 and 40 DT) (see table). Weed

dry weights in weeded plots were 12.94-15.80 g/m², compared to 45.2 g/m² in the unweeded.

Azolla with HW or in combination with preemergence herbicides had higher yields than the unweeded check, but lower than those with chemical treatments. The highest net returns were with butachlor + HW (\$687.4) and with 2 HW (\$664.2). □

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OTHER PESTS

Rat damage to rice seedlings in the hilly region of Karnataka, India

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Little is known about rice yield losses to rodents. To estimate loss of seedlings to rats *Bandicota bengalensis*, the number of rows per bed and percent of rows damaged in a bed were recorded. For analysis, partially damaged rows were averaged (two 50% damaged rows = one 100% damaged row). Rice seedlings in 10 randomly selected rows with no rat damage were counted to set the average number of seedlings per row for a rice nursery. For each sowing date, a control, rat-free nursery was maintained by repeated application of aluminum phosphide, a rodent burrow fumigant.

Soil was sandy loam; seeds were hand-sown in rows, 0.1 m apart.

Rats scooped out lumps of mud to feed on germinating rice seeds (see figure), damaging seedlings in the process. They caused significant losses to rice seedlings sown on 23 Jan and 31 Jul (see table). □

Rows of IR20 seedlings damaged by *Bandicota bengalensis* in Mudigere, India.

Losses of rice seedlings to *Bandicota bengalensis* in Mudigere, India, 1984-86.

Sowing date	Nursery bed size (m)	Rows/bed (no.)	Beds/nursery (no.)	Rows damaged (%)	Seedlings damaged/nursery	
					% ^a	F value ^b
23 Jan 1984	5 × 1 × 0.3	42	18	18.51	25.12 a (0.08)	P < 0.05
18 Jun	10 × 4 × 0.4	44	8	5.42	7.10 c (0.01)	P > 0.05
8 Jul	5 × 1 × 0.2	45	5	8.90	14.00 b (0.00)	P > 0.05
31 Jul	5 × 1 × 0.3	45	8	37.50	43.50 a (0.05)	P < 0.05
2 Jun 1986	5 × 2 × 0.3	45	8	2.10	3.15 c (0.00)	P > 0.05
22 May	5 × 2 × 0.3	45	5	3.80	4.60 c (0.00)	P > 0.05

^a Figures in parentheses correspond to control. Letters followed by the same letter are not statistically different by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b F values compared to control.

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